

CONTEXT OF ECO-PSYCHOLOGICAL IMBALANCE

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Abstract

In nature both conflict and cooperation go hand in hand. One forms the basis of destruction and the other of creation. Physical and biological things together form a large biological system. Man is an organism as well as a factor in the earth's ecosystem. He influences the environment through his imaginations and desires. By using the natural environment, man creates the cultural environment. The present man has become more progressive in his development, but he has disorganized the system of nature. Due to this disorder, the entire ecosystem has become a victim of degradation and pollution. The emotional weakness of man is also responsible for this. The vision of beauty and love towards nature is getting weaker due to which people's life is becoming weak, frustrated and repressed. In this research paper, the falling level of emotional relationship between man and his ecosystem has been studied. For which both primary and secondary data have been used.

Key Points: *Ecosystem, psychology, ecosystem-psychology, ecosystem-imbalance, spirituality, ecology, tree owner, laborer, trader.*

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Introduction: The web of interactions between organisms and their physical environment as well as the interrelationships between man and his environment is known as ecosystem. In other words, an ecosystem is such a geographical area where plants and animals, as well as the weather and topography, together create a vibrant environment for the creation and operation of life. The term ecosystem was first used by Arthur Tansley in 1935. This term was coined by Arthur Roy Clapham. In this way, each factor of the ecosystem contributes to the creation and operation of the life of the other factor. Its contribution can be in the form of direct and indirect washing. Ecosystem can be small and large depending on the region. Like mountain ecosystem, plateau ecosystem, plain ecosystem, desert ecosystem, urban ecosystem, pond ecosystem etc. In this way, the whole earth is deeply connected with each other's life. One organism is making each other alive and living by being embedded in the life of another organism. The way the circumstances are changing in the present times. Because of that, there is a change in the nature, structure and functioning of the ecosystem. This change is not positive for the existence of human beings along with the living beings of the ecosystem. Human economic activities are not only responsible for this. Man's thinking and feelings are also responsible for this. The discipline that studies the ecosystem is addressed as ecology. Ecology studies various aspects of the entire ecosystem in a logical and planned manner. Ecology also studies this aspect of how humans have used the earth's resources. What effect is it reading on the earth and in what way will it affect the human race to come? Ecology recognizes that the interrelationships between organisms in an ecosystem are extremely complex. There is a need for patience, subtle vision, scientific method and continuity to study it.

Using the principles of ecology and psychology, a method was developed to study the interrelationships between man and his ecosystem. Whose name is ecological psychology. Under ecological psychology, it studies the psychological interrelationships of human beings along with the living beings found in the ecosystem and their physical environment. How the psychology of man affects his environment and in turn how his environment affects the mental life of man, it would have been possible to study it under eco-psychology. At present, the psychological imbalance of mankind is responsible for the ecological imbalance crisis. Man is becoming ambitious, collector and heartless towards nature. The spirit of the world is taking a commercial form due to which the whole ecosystem is becoming unbalanced.

Research Methodology: Keeping in mind the research topic some major research methods will be used.

Research Objectives: The main research objectives of this research paper are,

- To know the psychological relationship between the ecosystem and man.
- To study the emotional condition of man towards the ecosystem.
- To study the tree spirituality of man towards the ecosystem.

Research Question:

- How is the psychological relationship between the ecosystem and man?
- What is the nature of human's emotional position towards the ecosystem?
- What is the position of man's tree spirituality towards the ecosystem?

Research Unit: The total number of research unit is 60. In which 25 tree selling farmers, 25 tree cutting laborers and 10 tree cutting traders are included.

Research Method: Interview schedule and observation have been used for the collection of data under this research form. Under this, analytical research format will be used for the analysis of the data.

Data analysis and generalization:

Table 1: Eco-psychological imbalance measure

S. No	Statement	Respondent	Dont know	C.disagree	Disagree	Agree	C. Agree	Total
1	Do you feel deep connection from your ecosystem?	Tree owner	0.0	8.0	3.0	64.0	25.0	100.0
		worker	33.8	0.0	13.8	52.5	0.0	100.0
		Trader	0.0	0.0	45.0	55.0	0.0	100.0
2	Do you think that your environment is alive organism unit?	Tree owner	0.0	0.0	5.0	91.0	4.0	100.0
		worker	10.0	0.0	5.0	85.0	0.0	100.0
		Trader	0.0	20.0	27.0	53.0	0.0	100.0
3	Do you praise your intellectuality of environment creature?	Tree owner	0.0	13.0	3.0	67.0	17.0	100.0
		worker	0.0	0.0	5.0	95.0	0.0	100.0
		Trader	0.0	0.0	45.0	50.0	5.0	100.0
4	Do you feel disconnection from your ecosystem?	Tree owner	0.0	0.0	37.0	54.0	9.0	100.0
		worker	0.0	2.5	86.3	11.3	0.0	100.0
		Trader	0.0	5.0	45.0	50.0	0.0	100.0
5	Do you think that you are part of big bio cycle of ecosystem?	Tree owner	0.0	3.0	7.0	64.0	26.0	100.0
		worker	0.0	0.0	2.5	68.8	28.8	100.0
		Trader	0.0	100	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
6	Do you think that all creature of your ecosystem like you?	Tree owner	0.0	27.0	37.0	17.0	19.0	100.0
		worker	0.0	1.3	46.3	52.5	0.0	100.0
		Trader	0.0	45.0	55.0	0.0	0.0	100.0

Table 1: Under the first aspect, tree seller respondents have the highest perception of 64% feeling a lack of ecological connection to their surroundings, while 25% seem to strongly agree. 52.5% of the respondents who cut trees agreed, while 33.8% did not know about the emotional attachment to the ecosystem. Under the business class, 55% people have expressed their consent, while 45% people have expressed their disagreement. In this way, in terms of feeling a sense of positive emotional connection with the ecosystem around them as a whole, tree sellers are in a better position than tree cutters and tree fellers.

An attempt has been made to know the view of the respondents towards the second aspect of Table 1, which is the ecosystem as a living community, in which maximum 91% of the respondents who sell trees have expressed their agreement, while 4% completely disagree. Agreed and only 5% of the respondents expressed their disagreement to consider the entire ecosystem as a vibrant community. And 85% of the working class who cut trees believe that they see the ecosystem around them as a living community. While only 53% people in the business class see the ecosystem around them as a vibrant community. While 27% traders seem to disagree, 20% completely agree. It is clear from this that as the consumerist view towards the ecosystem is increasing, instead of considering the ecosystem as a living community, the human view is becoming dominant as a commodity or a means for its consumption.

Under the third aspect of Table 1, which is about the happiness of the intelligence of the creatures in the ecosystem, 67% of the respondents who sell trees believe that they enjoy the intelligence of other creatures found in their ecosystem and their praise, while only 13% of tree owners strongly disagree with this approach. 95% of the working class who cut trees agree with and admire the intelligence of the creatures in the ecosystem around them, while only 50% of the business class agree. 45% traders' express disagreement. From which it is clear that due to the intelligence of the living beings found in the ecosystem, in the Indian society, due to being a part of the same God in the spiritual form, there is equality in the matter of intelligence and equality in the matter of quantity.

Under the fourth aspect of Table 1, which examines the disconnection from nature, 34% of the respondents who sell trees agree that they feel safe with the ecosystem around them, while 57% of the respondents who sell trees consider that the living beings around them are no different from the animals. Within the tree cutting labour class, 86.3% disagree, 11.3% agree and 2.5% strongly disagree. On the other hand, 50% agree, 45% disagree and 5% completely agree in the tree cutting business class. It is clear from these facts that there is a similar situation in all the three groups regarding the tendency to consider themselves separate from the

ecosystem. But through interview and group discussion, it was found that the attitude of the youth towards their nature in the business class is very commercial, while the attitude of the respondents who sell trees is emotional.

The fifth aspect of Table 1 seeks to find out the respondents' view of being part of the biological cycle of the ecosystem. Under which 64% of the respondents who sell trees agree, 26% completely agree, 7% disagree and 3% completely disagree. 68.8% agree, 28.8% strongly agree, 2.5% disagree and 100% strongly disagree among tree felling traders. It is clear from these data that the feeling of considering the entire ecosystem as a biological unit, human and self as an integral part of it is maximum among the respondents who sell trees. Right around the same is the condition of the tree cutting workers. Both of these are equal because the working-class cutting trees has a deeper connection with nature, awareness of nature has arisen in it, and it cuts trees only considering it as a means of its livelihood. There are comparatively not many feelings like loss and profit behind cutting trees in it.

An attempt has been made to study the status of the respondents' eco-psychology by linking the sixth aspect of Table 1, animals and plants with the human race. Under which 37% disagree, 17% agree, 19% completely agree and 27% completely disagree among the respondents who sell trees. Among the working class who cut trees, 55% disagree, 45% strongly agree. On the other hand, 70% disagree and 30% completely disagree in the tree cutting business class. It is clear from these facts that the tendency of the respondents to consider the animals found in the ecosystem as a whole as their own caste has become around 50%, in which the business class and labour class are in the worst condition if seen comparatively. While the condition of the householders who sell trees is fine. Through interview and group discussion, it was found that the merchant class has a professional attitude towards flora and fauna. Due to keeping, he refuses to consider them as belonging to his caste community and considers them as a means of his enjoyment, which presents a growing situation towards ecological-psychological imbalance.

Answers of research questions:

- **How is the psychological relationship between the ecosystem and man?**

The obtained data clearly shows that the feeling of man towards the ecosystem is getting distorted in the study area. The changing thinking of man is responsible behind the perverted feeling. Capitalistic, collectivist, individualistic thinking has greatly spoiled the emotional condition of man, due to which the relationship between man and his environment is getting weaker. Environmental imbalance is increasing due to this weakness.

● **What is the nature of human's emotional position towards the ecosystem?**

The emotional condition of man towards the ecosystem is getting weaker. The commercial outlook towards life is emotionally distorting man towards nature, due to which human life is becoming a victim of emotional crisis. In this way, the situation of emotional deviation is increasing. The condition of the people of the study area is telling that on one hand the emotional condition is moderate and on the other hand it is continuously getting weaker.

● **What is the position of man's tree spirituality towards the ecosystem?**

The statistics of the study area show that the pace at which physical development is increasing, people are using trees and plants for infrastructural development. Due to which trees are being cut on a large scale. The trees which people used to worship earlier, today they are destroying those trees because of their indulgence. If seen in this way, the spiritual condition of the tree is getting weaker.

Conclusion: Eco-spirituality is an important concept which has been created from the interaction between environment and psychology. This research paper indicates that people's view towards the ecosystem is becoming commercial. Its effect is being seen negatively towards trees as well. Emotional deviation is increasing due to which violence towards nature is increasing in people's lives. It is also having a bad effect on human life. Due to moving away from nature, human life is becoming a victim of blood pressure, diabetes, depression etc. It is a natural crisis as well as a human crisis.

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